

Probing the metallating ability of a polybasic sodium alkylmagnesiates supported by a bulky bis(amido) ligand: deprotomagnesiation reactions of nitrogen-based aromatic substrates

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Exploring the reactivity of sodium butylmagnesiates reagent $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_6\}^+\{\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2\text{Mg}(\text{Bu})(\text{THF})\}]$ (1) supported by the bulky chelating silyl(bisamido) ligand $\{\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2\}^{2-}$ ($\text{Ar}^* = 2,6\text{-iPr}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$) towards *N*-methylbenzimidazole (blm^{Me}), pyrrole and 2,6-diisopropylaniline (NH_2Ar^*), this study provides new insights into the ability of this bimetallic base to facilitate direct Mg–H exchange reactions as well as to exhibit polybasicity. Thus 1 effectively promotes the deprotomagnesiation of blm^{Me} under mild reaction conditions to give the α -metallated intermediate $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_6\}^+\{\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2\text{Mg}(\text{blm}^{\text{Me}*})\}]_2$ (2) ($\text{blm}^{\text{Me}*} = 2\text{-}N\text{-methylbenzimidazolyl}$). Analysis of crystallographic and NMR data of 2 combined with DFT calculations show that the metallated C in the $\text{blm}^{\text{Me}*}$ ligands possesses a significant carbenic character. Contrasting with previous studies of benzothiazole (btz), 1 does not react with an excess of blm^{Me} even under forcing refluxing conditions. Contrastingly, the amination reactions of equimolar amounts of 1 with pyrrole and 2,6-diisopropylaniline allowed the isolation of $[\{\{\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)(\text{NHAr}^*)\}\text{Mg}(\text{NC}_4\text{H}_4)_2(\text{THF})\text{Na}(\text{THF})_2\}]$ (3) and $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_6\}^+\{\{\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)(\text{NHAr}^*)\}\text{Mg}(\text{NHAr}^*)_2(\text{THF})\}]$ (4) respectively as crystalline solids.

Highlighting the ability of 1 to act as a polybasic reagent, 3 and 4 are formed as the result of the deprotonation of two molecules of the relevant amine *via* its butyl group and one amido arm of the silyl(bisamido) ligand. Similarly, the reactions of 1 with 3 molar equivalents of the relevant amine yielded homoleptic tris(amido) compounds $[(\text{THF})_2\text{NaMg}(\text{NC}_4\text{H}_4)_3]$ (5) and $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_6\}^+\{\text{Mg}(\text{NHAr}^*)_3\}]$ (7), with the concomitant formation of bis(amine) $\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NHAr}^*)_2$, as a result of the complete amination of 1 using its three basic sites. The structures in the solid state of 3 and 4 were elucidated by X-ray crystallography. Despite their similar constitution, these heteroleptic tris(amido)magnesiates adopt contrasting structures, with the former displaying a contacted ion-pair structure, where Na and Mg are connected by two bridging pyrrolyl anions, whereas the latter gives rise to a solvent-separated ion pair motif. To the best of our knowledge 3 represents the first crystallographically characterized magnesium compound containing an anionic non-substituted form of pyrrole. Noticeably, Mg interacts exclusively with the N atoms of the pyrrolyl ligands, forming strong σ -bonds, whereas Na prefers to engage with the π -systems of both NC_4 -rings.

Introduction

The synthesis of magnesium compounds supported by sterically demanding ligands, such as β -diketiminates, guanidates, *N*-heterocyclic carbenes or bis(amides), is attracting increasing widespread interest.¹ Providing a protective steric shelter, the use of these ligands has been instrumental in recent landmarks in Mg chemistry, which include the isolation of the first stable Mg–Mg bonded compounds,² as well as the trapping of novel high nuclearity magnesium-hydride clusters, having important implications as models for hydrogen

storage.³ Within the context of catalysis, magnesium complexes supported by β -diketiminato ligands have proved to be extremely active single-site initiators for polymerisation of *rac*-lactide⁴ as well as efficient precatalysts for intramolecular hydroamination reactions of a wide range of aminoalkenes.⁵ Contrastingly, the effects bulky ligands may have on the reactivity/structures of alkali-metal magnesiates compounds remain largely unstudied. This is particularly surprising as members of this mixed-metal family are versatile and efficient polar

organometallic reagents, finding extensive applications in many important synthetic transformations, including nucleophilic alkylation, magnesium–halogen exchange or deprotonation (C–H bond breaking) reactions, to name a few.⁶ By operating synergistically, alkali-metal magnesiate can exhibit superior chemo- and regioselectivities and/or functional group tolerances to conventional monometallic reagents. Recent breakthroughs in this area include Knochel's turbo Grignard reagents RMgCl·LiCl, whose enhanced nucleophilicity allows direct magnesiation (*via* Mg–halogen exchange reactions) of aromatic molecules with sensitive organic functional groups, without the need for cryogenic conditions,⁷ as well as the use of heterobimetallic amides in alkali-metal-mediated magnesiation (AMMMg) processes to facilitate in certain cases the regioselective deprotonation of organic substrates in remote positions, not available using single-metal bases.⁸ We recently reported the synthesis of the solvent-separated sodium magnesiate $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_6\}^+\{(\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2)\text{Mg}(\text{Bu})(\text{THF})\}^-]$ (**1**) resulting from the reaction of homoleptic NaMgBu₃ with the silyl-bis(amine) precursor Ph₂Si(NHAr^{*})₂, which contains bulky 2,6-diisopropylphenyl substituents (Ar^{*}).⁹ On treatment with benzothiazole (btz), **1** is transformed to the complex molecular assembly $[\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}_2(\text{L1})_2(\text{THF})_5]$, where L1 is a novel trianionic ligand resulting from the deprotonation and coupling of three btz molecules, one of which ring opens (Scheme 1; the proposed mechanism for this cascade process involving magnesiation, C–C coupling, ring opening, nucleophilic addition and intramolecular deprotonation is depicted in Scheme S1 in ESI file†). The unique outcome of this activation process contrasts sharply with the straightforward reactivity reported for more conventional organomagnesium reagents such as Hauser bases or Grignard reagents, which can readily deprotonate btz

Scheme 1 Magnesium-mediated cascade activation of btz.

at its C2 position in quantitative yields.¹⁰ Our initial studies show that rather than act as a mere spectator, the bis(amido) ligand $\{\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2\}^{2-}$ plays a prominent role in facilitating this cascade of fast intramolecular reactions, acting as a base through both its amido arms with concomitant formation of bis(amine) Ph₂Si(NHAr^{*})₂ (Scheme 1).⁹ Furthermore, it appears that the deprotonation of the first molecule of btz, by the Bu base in **1**, is the rate determining step in the process. Further evidence supporting this proposal has been found by investigating the reactivity of btz with β-diketiminato stabilised magnesium reagents, which show that a closely related cascade activation process is also in operation when a kinetically resilient butyl derivative is employed, although in this case the β-diketiminato ligand acts as a steric stabiliser rather than a base.¹¹

Stimulated by these intriguing initial findings and aiming to gain a better understanding of the metallating ability of sodium magnesiate **1** and its involvement in the above mentioned btz activation process, herein we extend our reactivity studies towards the related 1,3-benzazole *N*-methylbenzimidazole (bIm^{Me}) as well as exploring its amination reactions with the amines pyrrole and 2,6-diisopropylphenylamine, NH₂Ar^{*}.

Results and discussion

Direct magnesiation of *N*-methylbenzimidazole

We started our studies by studying the reaction of sodium magnesiate **1** with *N*-methylbenzimidazole bIm^{Me} whose hydrogen atom at the C2 position between the N atoms is substantially less acidic than that in benzothiazole (calculated p*K*_a values, 32.5 for bIm^{Me} vs. 27.5 for btz).¹² The room-temperature 1 : 1 reaction in THF solution afforded a pale green solution which on cooling deposited a crop of yellow crystals of $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_5\}^+\{(\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2)\text{Mg}(\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}*})\}^-]$ (**2**) (bIm^{Me*} = 2-*N*-methylbenzimidazolyl) in a 71% isolated yield (Scheme 2).

X-ray crystallographic studies of **2** confirmed that C2-magnesiation of bIm^{Me} has taken place, giving rise to a solvent separated ion pair complex containing two sodium cations, each solvated by five THF molecules, and a novel dinuclear dianion comprising two $\{(\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2)\text{Mg}\}$ fragments connected by two bridging *N*-methylbenzimidazolyl bIm^{Me*} ligands. These ligands coordinate in an asymmetric fashion *via* their metalated carbon and one of their N atoms (C1 and N1 in Fig. 1). This distinct bonding mode closes a six-membered $\{\text{MgCNMgCN}\}$ ring, which is fused through each of its Mg

Scheme 2 Direct magnesiation of bIm^{Me} using sodium magnesiate **1**.

Fig. 1 Structure of the anion of 2 with displacement ellipsoids drawn at the 50% probability level and hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°): Mg–N1 2.091(2), Mg–C1A 2.233(3), Mg–N3 2.028(2), Mg–N4 2.160(2), C1–N1 1.362(3), C1–N2 1.380(3), N3–Mg–N4 76.74(4), N3–Mg–N1 118.00(9), N1–Mg–C1A 102.91(10), N4–Mg–C1A 124.85(9), N3–Mg–C1A 116.18(10), N4–Mg–N1 118.32(9), Si–N4–Mg 89.54(9), MgA–C1–N2 123.14(18), MgA–C1–N1 129.24(19), N1–C1–N2 106.9(2). The suffix A denotes an inversion-related atom.

vertices to a four-membered {MgNSiN} ring, resulting from the coordination of the bis(amido) ligand to Mg. The distorted tetrahedral geometry of Mg [bond angles ranging from 76.74(4) to 124.85(9)°; mean 109.41°] indicates an approximately orthogonal disposition of this 4-6-4 fused ring system. This structural motif has a strong resemblance with that recently reported for deprotonation of bIm^{Me} using a homometallic Mg amido base supported by the β -diketiminato ligand nacnac (nacnac = Ar*NC(Me)CHC(Me)NAr*, Ar* = 2,6-*i*-Pr₂-C₆H₃) as it also exhibits a dimeric arrangement with a central six-membered ring,¹¹ although in this case no discussion of its geometrical parameters was possible due to the low precision of the structure. A comparison of Mg–N_{bis(amido)} bond distances in 2 shows a noticeable asymmetry in the coordination of this chelating ligand to the Mg centre [Mg–N4, 2.160(2) Å vs. Mg–N3, 2.028(2) Å], which could be attributed to the steric constraints imposed by the rigid tricyclic structure of 2. Interestingly, it should also be noted that the Mg–N_{bIm^{Me}*} bond length in 2 [Mg–N1, 2.091(2) Å] lies in the same range of these Mg–N_{amido} values, and is considerably shorter than that reported in the related Mg complex [(nacnac)Mg(Bu)(bIm^{Me})] [Mg–N1, 2.144(2) Å],¹¹ where bIm^{Me} coordinates as a neutral N-donor to Mg, hinting at the presence of at least some partial negative character of the nitrogen atom. Moreover, despite the sp² character of C, the Mg–C bond distance [Mg–C1A, 2.233(3) Å] is distinctly elongated compared to that of the butyl precursor 1 which also contains a similar pseudotetrahedral Mg environment [Mg–C_{Bu}, 2.124(3) Å].⁹ This, coupled with the subtle but noticeable variation of the N–C bonds of the imidazolyl rings [C1–N1, 1.362(3) Å; C1–N2, 1.380(3) Å] when compared to those of related 5-amino-1-methyl-benzimidazole [1.3785(18) and 1.350(2)]¹³ suggest that these bridging ligands exhibit a noticeable carbenic character, and therefore 2 can be envisaged as a 1-methyl-3-[magnesium bis(amido)]benzimidazol-2-ylidene dimer. Supporting this interpretation, the Mg–C bond distance in 2 is within the range of other values reported

for Mg–N-heterocyclic carbene complexes [ranging from 2.200(2) to 2.288(5) Å].¹⁴ Closely related, seminal studies by Boche *et al.* on the structure of lithiated 1-methyl-4-*tert*-butyl-imidazole have also established the significant carbenic character of the imidazolyl ligands, by eloquently comparing the structural differences of this compound with those found for imidazole and for the related NHC 1,3-bis(1-adamantyl-imidazol-2-ylidene).^{15,16} Interestingly, the coordination flexibility of imidazolyl ligands has recently been highlighted by Hayton *et al.* for the synthesis of bimetallic compounds containing uranyl-nacnac fragments, where the binding modes of these ligands to U (as carbanions or N donors in their carbene resonance form) can be finely controlled by modifying the electronic properties of the accompanying metal.¹⁷ Contrasting with this tunability, computational studies on the tautomerization of free imidazole to its NHC form show that this process is energetically unfavoured, being endothermic by almost 30 kcal mol⁻¹.¹⁸ However, it should be noted that by using a stepwise strategy of sequential deprotonation and electrophilic interception, recent studies in d-block chemistry have revealed the effective transformation of *N*-alkyl imidazoles coordinated to transition metal fragments to N-heterocyclic carbenes.¹⁹

Solubility in deuterated THF enabled 2 to be characterized in solution using ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy (see the Experimental section for details). The most informative resonance in the ¹³C NMR spectrum appears at 194.0 ppm for the

C2 carbon of bIm^{Me*} which is significantly downfield compared to the C2 resonance observed in free bIm^{Me} (142.7 ppm) and also noticeably different from that reported for the metallated C of an α -magnesiated *N*-methylindole species (181.1 ppm).²⁰ Supporting the interpretation of the solid-state studies, reflecting the markedly carbenic character of the bIm^{Me*} ligands in 2, this chemical shift corresponds more closely to those previously reported for the C_{carbene} in NHC–Mg complexes such as adduct ⁿBu₈Mg₄·2IPr (IPr = 1,3-bis-(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazol-2-ylidene) which resonates at 197.3 ppm.^{14f}

Remarkably both ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of 2 displayed well resolved signals with no detectable resonances that could be assigned to a ring-open α -(isocyano)methylanilide species, resulting from the cleavage of the C–N_{Me} bond of the bIm^{Me*} groups. This contrasts with previous NMR studies carried out for 2-lithiated-benzimidazole which show the existence of an equilibrium at room temperature between its ring-opened and ring-closed isomers.²¹

To probe the energetics involved in the formation of 2, theoretical calculations at the DFT level employing the B3LYP method²² and the 6-311G** basis set were used to model the metallation reaction of bIm^{Me} by sodium magnesiate 1 (see ESI† for details), showing that the formation of 2 (modelled as monomer 2A) is favoured by –13.9 kcal mol⁻¹.²³ This energy gain is even more substantial when considering the dimeric structure exhibited by 2 in the solid state, as the dimerization of 2A to give dimer 2B was estimated to be exothermic by –71.4 kcal mol⁻¹.²⁴

Comparing the calculated geometrical parameters of 2B with those determined experimentally from the X-ray crystallographic studies of 2 shows, in general, an excellent agreement (see Table 1 for selected bond distances and angles), with a slight overestimation for the calculated Mg–N1 bond [2.144 Å (calc.) vs. 2.091(2) Å (exp)]. Interestingly, when comparing the relative stabilities of the two possible isomers of monomeric 2A, as an *N*-metallacarbene (2A₁) or its carbanionic resonance (2A₂) (Fig. 2), it was found that the former is negligibly more stable (by 1.6 kcal mol⁻¹), which supports previous experimental findings on the bonding flexibility of imidazolyl ligands when coordinated to metal centres. It should be noted that in model 2A₁, the imidazolyl ligand coordinates to magnesium in an η²-fashion through its C and N atoms, forming a relatively short Mg–N bond with the imidazolyl ligand (2.099 Å), which is comparable with the Mg–N bond distance found experimentally in 2 (2.091(2) Å) as well as a Mg–C contact (2.163 Å) which is slightly elongated compared to that calculated for 2A₂ (2.133 Å) where Mg binds solely to the carbon of the bIm^{Me}* ligand. Related η²-(N,C)-coordination has been experimentally observed for the structures of lithiated 1-methyl-4-*tert*-butylimidazole and benzothiazole.¹⁵ Dimerization of 2A₁ to form 2B results in the cleavage of this Mg–C bond to generate a new bond with the Mg centre of a

neighbouring monomer. Consistent with its carbene resonance form, the difference between the calculated N–C bond distances of the imidazolyl ring in 2A₁ is significantly more subtle [$\Delta(d_{C-N}-d_{CNMe}) = 0.022$ Å] than that computed for 2A₂ [$\Delta(d_{C-N}-d_{CNMe}) = 0.067$ Å], supporting a more localised N–CvN_{Me} bonding scenario for the latter, similar to that calculated for the parent *N*-methylbenzimidazole (see ESI† for details, $\Delta(d_{C-N}-d_{CNMe}) = 0.073$ Å). Furthermore, a comparison of these theoretical values with that found experimentally in 2 [$\Delta(d_{C1-N2}-d_{C1N2}) = 0.018$ Å] offers further support to the carbenic character attributed to its bIm^{Me}* bridges on the basis of the X-ray crystallographic and NMR spectroscopic studies.

The regioselective C2-magnesiumation of bIm^{Me} by 1 differs significantly from the reactivity previously reported for related 1,3-benzazole, btz, where the three potential basic arms of 1 react with the heterocycle, even when 1 : 1 mixtures of these starting materials are employed, to form the complicated activation product [Na₂Mg₂L₂(THF)₅] depicted in Scheme 1.⁹ Furthermore, no further metallation was observed when isolated crystals of 2 were confronted with a 2 molar excess of bIm^{Me}, even when the mixture was heated at 65 °C over a 5 hour period, evidencing the resilience of the amido groups of the {Ph₂Si(NAr*)₂} ligand to promote the deprotonation of bIm^{Me}. Notwithstanding, considering that for the activation of btz the rate-determining step appears to be its metallation by the butyl group 1, 2 can be envisaged as an indirect model for the first intermediate involved in this cascade activation process, which in turn reacts with two further equivalents of btz to form the final product (Scheme 1 and S1 in ESI†). Interestingly, it should also be noted that the exclusive alkyl basicity displayed by 1 diverges from the reactivity reported for related homometallic magnesium β-diketiminates [(nacnac)Mg(Bu)(THF)], which fails to metallate, even under refluxing conditions, leading to the isolation of a simple coordination product, resulting from substitution of the THF molecule coordinated to Mg by a molecule of bIm^{Me}, acting as a neutral 2 electron-donor.¹¹ The enhanced metallating ability of 1 over neutral [(nacnac)Mg(Bu)(THF)] can be rationalised in terms of its bimetallic anionic ate constitution, which enables the activation of an otherwise kinetically retarded butyl group.²⁵ Illustrating this activating effect, Mulvey has reported the high-yielding room temperature α-magnesiumation of *N*-methylindole using sodium tetrabutylmagnesiates [(TMEDA)₂NaMgBu₄], where each Bu group reacts with one equivalent of the substrate, whereas MgBu₂ on its own fails to deprotonate this same heterocycle.²⁰

Extension to pyrrole and 2,6-diisopropylaniline: polybasic behaviour of magnesiates base

In order to explore the possibility of 1 acting as a polybasic reagent, we next turned our attention to the heterocyclic amine pyrrole. Its *N*-*H* group has a pK_a value of 23 making it significantly more acidic than the C₂-*H* of bIm^{Me}.²⁶ Surprisingly, we found that even when equimolar amounts of this substrate and mixed-metal base 1 were employed, compound [{(Ph₂Si(NAr*)(NHAr*))Mg(NC₄H₄)₂(THF)Na(THF)₂}] (3), resulting from

Table 1 Comparison of selected calculated bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for model 2B with those from the X-ray crystallographic data of 2

	2	2B
Mg–N1	2.091(2)	2.144
Mg–C1A	2.233(3)	2.270
Mg–N3	2.028(3)	2.082
Mg–N4	2.160(2)	2.210
C1–N1	1.362(2)	1.357
C1–N2	1.380(3)	1.384
N1–Mg–C1A	102.9(10)	100.8
N3–C1–N1	118.00(9)	107.6
N3–Mg–N4	76.74(4)	76.4

Fig. 2 Modelled structures and selected calculated bond distances and angles for the anionic moieties of monomeric 2A₁ and 2A₂.

Scheme 3 Amination reactions of 1 with pyrrole and 2,6-diisopropylaniline.

the deprotonation of two molecules of pyrrole, *via* the butyl group and amido arm of the bis(amido) ligand present in 1, was obtained in a 17% isolated yield (Scheme 3) as a crystalline product. Compound 3 was characterized by multinuclear ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy and its structure elucidated by X-ray crystallography, which confirmed its bimetallic constitution (see the Experimental section and ESI† for details). Interestingly, when the rational synthesis of 3 was attempted by reacting butylmagnesiates 1 with two molar equivalents of pyrrole at room temperature, compound 3 was obtained as a crystalline solid along with variable amounts of tris(amido)

$[(\text{THF})_2\text{NaMg}(\text{NC}_4\text{H}_4)_3]$ (5), with the later resulting from the complete amination of 1 involving its three potentially basic arms. The formation of this compound can be significantly minimised by carrying out the addition of the amine at 0 °C, which affords 3 in an improved 57% yield (see the Experimental section for details).²⁷ Tris(pyrrolyl)magnesiates 5 was characterised by ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy and could be prepared and isolated in a 49% yield by treating 1 with 3 equivalents of pyrrole (see Table S2 and ESI† for details).²⁸

Highlighting the complexity of these amination reactions, extending these studies to the primary amine 2,6-diisopropylaniline, led to the formation of complicated mixtures of products. Thus, the reaction of equimolar amounts of this aniline and 1 deposited a few colourless crystals of the double

amination product $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_6\}^+\{\text{(Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)(\text{NHAr}^*))\text{Mg}(\text{NHAr}^*)_2(\text{THF})\}^-]$ (4),²⁹ the structure of which was determined in the solid state by X-ray crystallography (Fig. 4). However, ^1H NMR analysis of the solution filtrate showed that the major product of the reaction was $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_6\}^+\{\text{(Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2\text{Mg}(\text{NHAr}^*)(\text{THF})\}^-]$ (6), resulting from the reaction of the butyl group of 1 with the amine (Scheme 3). Contrastingly, ^1H NMR monitoring of the reaction of 1 with two molar equivalents of the aniline afforded a complex mixture of the three possible amination products 4, 6 and tris(anilido) $[\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_6\}^+\{\text{Mg}(\text{NHAr}^*)_3\}^-]$ (7) in a 1 : 2.1 : 1.1 ratio,³⁰ whereas when three equivalents of NH_2Ar were employed, compound 1 was quantitatively converted into tris(anilido) 7 and bis(amine) $\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NHAr})_2$.³¹

Despite their similar tris(amido) constitution, sodium magnesiates 3 and 4 exhibit remarkably different structures in the solid state (Fig. 3 and 4, respectively). Although in both cases Mg displays a similar coordination environment, adopting a distorted four-coordinate tetrahedral geometry (mean angle

Fig. 3 Molecular structure of 3 with displacement ellipsoids drawn at the 50% probability level and hydrogen atoms (except NH) and minor disorder components in THF ligand are omitted for clarity. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°): Na–O3 2.265(2), Na–O2 2.294(16), Na–N3 2.635(2), Na–N4 2.796(2), Na–C37 2.721(3), Na–C38 3.002(3), Na–C39 3.066(3), Na–C40 2.837(3), Na–C41 3.016(3), Na–C42 3.137(3), Na–C43 2.960(3), Na–C44 2.729(3), Mg–O1 2.033(17), Mg–N1 2.015(18), Mg–N3 2.0514(19), Mg–N4 2.060(2), N1–Mg–O1 115.23(7), N1–Mg–N3 114.99(8), O1–Mg–N3 99.54(7), N1–Mg–N4 123.27(8), O1–Mg–N4 100.61(8), N3–Mg–N4 99.46(8).

Fig. 4 Structure of anion moiety in 4 with displacement ellipsoids drawn at the 50% probability level and hydrogen atoms (except NHs) are omitted for clarity.

around Mg 108.85° for 3 and 108.88° for 4), being bound by two newly formed amide ligands as well as terminal amido(silyl)amine $\{\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)(\text{NHAr}^*)\}$ and a solvating molecule of THF, 3 displays a contacted-ion pair structure, where Na and Mg are connected by two pyrrolyl bridges, whereas in 4, Na is solvated by six molecules of THF, giving rise to a solvent-separated ion pair motif. In both cases the new amine NHAr^* group, generated by protonation of the chelating bis(amido) ligand of 1, does not interact with the Mg centre, which instead prefers coordination by a molecule of the donor solvent THF. This coordination preference contrasts with that found in the lithium dimer $[\{\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(2,6\text{-Et}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH})(2,6\text{-Et}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NLi})\}_2]$ which contains a similar amido(silyl)amine, bonding in a chelating fashion *via* its two N atoms to Li.³² Unfortunately, the structure of 4 was derived from a twinned and weakly diffracting crystal sample and also features considerable disorder with respect to the THF groups. Thus, despite several attempts at data collection, the final model is

of a relatively low precision, which prevents discussion of any geometrical parameters, although its connectivity is definite.³³

The structure of **3** is notable for having distinct bonding preferences of Na and Mg to the pyrrolyl anions. Thus, while Mg coordinates exclusively in a σ -manner forming relatively short (strong) Mg–N bonds [Mg–N3, 2.0514(19) Å and Mg–N4 2.060(2) Å], Na engages with the π -systems of both pyrrolyl NC₄-rings. The pattern of the bond distances in these Na $\cdots\pi$ -face interactions denotes η^5 -NC₄ coordination, with noticeably shorter Na \cdots N contacts [Na–N3, 2.635(2) Å and Na–N4, 2.796(2) Å] than the remaining Na \cdots C [ranging from 2.721(3) to 3.066(3) Å and from 2.729(3) to 3.137(3) Å for each NC₄ ring], which can be attributed to the more electron-rich character of the amido N atoms. Furthermore, in order to maximize this Na $\cdots\pi$ -surface bonding, both pyrrolyl rings are tilted towards the Na cation, as evidenced by the narrow N3–Mg–N4 bond angle [99.46(8)°]. Reflecting the isoelectronic and close structural relationship between pyrrolyl and cyclopentadienyl (C₅H₅, Cp) rings, the η^5 -NC₄ π -bonding present in **3** bears a strong resemblance to that found in other NaCp species which have been structurally elucidated, as for example polymeric [$\{Na(DME)(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_-\}$] (DME = 1,2-dimethoxyether).³⁴ Interestingly, a similar σ/π bonding distinction to that observed in **3** has been recently described by Mulvey *et al.* for a series of sodium-zincate pyrrolyl complexes.³⁵ Contrastingly, this earlier study reveals that, in the homometallic sodium derivative [$\{PMDETA\}Na(NC_4H_4)_2$], the Na cation interacts only with the N atoms of the pyrrolyl units, avoiding any possible π -contact with the aromatic ring,³⁵ which suggests that for heterobimetallic **3**, the metal–N σ bonding preference of the NC₄H₄ is dictated by the stronger Lewis acidity of Mg in comparison to Na. As far as we can ascertain, **3** represents the first crystallographically characterized magnesium compound containing an anionic non-substituted form of pyrrole.³⁶

The ¹H NMR spectrum of **3** in deuterated benzene solution showed a broad singlet at 4.10 ppm for the NH group and two diagnostic multiplets for the CH groups of the ⁱPr substituents of the amido(silyl)amine {Ph₂Si(NAr*)(NHAr*)} ligand at 4.48 and 2.79 ppm which can be assigned to its amido NAr* and amine NHAr* arms, respectively.³⁷ Reflecting the increased negative charge of the N centres of the pyrrolyl ligands in **3** in comparison with the N–H unit in pyrrole, the signals attributed to the α -positions of the heterocycle in both ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra appear significantly more shielded (at 6.50 and 136.6 ppm, respectively) than to those found for free pyrrole (at 6.37 and 117.5 ppm, respectively).³⁸ This effect is even more pronounced for tris(amido) [(THF)₂NaMg(NC₄H₄)₃] (**5**) whose α -H's appear at 7.69 ppm in its ¹H NMR spectrum (Table S2, ESI†).

Collectively, these findings from the amination reactions of **1** demonstrate the ability of the bis(amido) ligand {Ph₂Si(NAr)₂} present within sodium magnesiate **1** to participate in Mg–H exchange processes, converting, in this case, the N–H bonds of either pyrrole or 2,6-diisopropylaniline, into new Mg–N bonds. Furthermore, the fact that these conversions take place even with equimolar amounts of **1** and the relevant amine shows that depending on the activation level of the substrate employed, **1** can execute polybasic behaviour even

under substoichiometric conditions, using its amido arms. Thus rather than act as a spectator, providing a steric shield to the Mg centre, this bis(amido) ligand can also play a prominent role in facilitating the metallation of more than one molecule of the substrate by the bimetallic base, which in some cases can lead to a Mg centre coordinating simultaneously to several sensitive anions, facilitating activation processes like the one depicted in Scheme 1 for btz.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that sodium magnesiate **1**, which is supported by the bulky chelating bis(amido) ligand {Ph₂Si(NAr*)₂}, can effectively promote direct Mg–H exchange reactions. Thus, the metallation products of its reaction with bIm^{Me} and the amines pyrrole and 2,6-diisopropylaniline, **2**, **3** and **4**, respectively, have been isolated and structurally elucidated. Contrastingly with our previous reactivity studies with the related 1,3-benzoazole btz, **1** acts exclusively as a butyl base towards bIm^{Me}, facilitating its selective C2-metallation affording **2**. X-ray crystallographic studies of **2** established its dimeric constitution, containing an unusual dinuclear magnesiate dianion, where the benzimidazolyl ligands coordinate asymmetrically through their metallated C and N atoms to the Mg centres. Analysis of its crystallographic and NMR spectroscopic data coupled with DFT studies revealed that the Mg–C atoms of the bIm^{Me}* fragments of **2** display a significant carbenic character. Reactivity studies show that even under forcing refluxing conditions and using an excess of bIm^{Me}, the potentially basic arms of the bis(amido) ligand in **1** are unable to deprotonate this N-heterocyclic molecule. Notwithstanding, **2** can be envisaged as a model for the first intermediate proposed to be involved in the cascade activation of btz mediated by **1**, where the rate-determining step appears to be the deprotonation of btz by the butyl group of **1**. Establishing the ability of **1** to execute polybasicity, its reactions with equimolar amounts of the amines pyrrole and 2,6-diisopropylaniline led to the isolation of the double amination products **3** and **4** as crystalline solids. Varying the stoichiometry of these reactions has shown that complete amination of **1**, using its butyl group and two amido arms of the bulky chelating ligand, can be accomplished using 3 equivalents of the relevant amine, allowing the isolation of homoleptic tris(amido)magnesiates **5** and **7**.

Collectively these findings shed new light on the reactivity of **1**, unveiling its potential to execute selective deprotomagnesiation reaction, as well as providing new mechanistic insights into its role in the cascade activation of btz, where **1** uses all three of its basic arms to formally deprotonate three molecules of this heterocycle.

Experimental section

Synthesis of [$\{\text{Na}(\text{THF})_5\}_2^+\{(\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)_2)\text{Mg}(\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}^*})\}_2^-$] (2)

1-Methylbenzimidazole (0.13 g, 1 mmol) was added to a solution of isolated crystals of 1 (1.14 g, 1 mmol) in THF (3 ml) affording a pale green solution that was stirred at room temperature for 2 hours. Hexane (5 ml) was added and the resulting solution was transferred to a freezer ($-30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). After 48 hours, a crop of yellow crystals was isolated (0.76 g, 71%). ^1H NMR (d_8 -THF, 298 K) δ 7.76 [d, 4H, Ph], 6.99 [m, 6H, Ph], 6.95 [m, 1H, MebIm*], 6.94 [m, 1H, bIm^{Me*}], 6.88 [d, 4H, Ar*], 6.59 [t, 2H, Ar*], 6.33 [m, 1H, bIm^{Me*}], 6.12 [t, 1H, bIm^{Me*}], 4.10 [m, 4H, CH, ⁱPr, Ar*], 3.61 [m, 20H, OCH₂, THF], 3.51 [s, 3H, CH₃, bIm^{Me*}], 1.76 [m, 20H, CH₂, THF], 0.78 [d, 24H, CH₃, ⁱPr, Ar*]. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (d_8 -THF, 298 K) δ 194.0 [C–Mg], 155.9, 155.3, 148.5, 145.4, 143.4 [C_{quaternary}, Ph, Ar* and bIm^{Me*}], 136.9 [CH, Ph], 127.6 [CH, Ph], 127.4 [CH, Ph], 123.8 [CH, Ar*], 123.1, 121.0, 120.6 [CH, bIm^{Me*}], 117.5 [CH, Ar*], 116.8 [CH, bIm^{Me*}], 68.2 [O–CH₂, THF], 34.6 [CH₃, bIm^{Me*}], 29.3 [CH, ⁱPr, Ar*], 27.3 [CH₃, ⁱPr, Ar*], 26.3 [CH₂, THF].

Synthesis of [$\{(\text{Ph}_2\text{Si}(\text{NAr}^*)(\text{NHAr}^*))\text{Mg}(\text{NC}_4\text{H}_4)_2(\text{THF})\text{Na}(\text{THF})_2\}$] (3)

Pyrrole (0.07 ml, 1 mmol) was added to a solution of sodium magnesiate 1 (1.14 g, 1 mmol) in hexane (5 ml), affording a suspension which was stirred at room temperature for 30 minutes. THF (4 ml) was introduced and the suspension gently heated until all the solid was dissolved affording a pale yellow solution. This solution was transferred to the freezer ($-30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and colourless crystals were obtained after 4 days, which were isolated by filtration and transferred to the glove box (isolated yield 0.155 g, 17%, note that employing this stoichiometry, the maximum possible yield for 3, with respect to 1 is 50%). This yield could be improved to 57% (0.530 g) when two equivalents (0.14 ml, 2 mmol) of pyrrole were employed, carrying out the amination reaction at $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to minimize the formation of tris(amido)magnesiate [$(\text{THF})_2\text{NaMg}(\text{NC}_4\text{H}_4)_3$] (5).³⁴ ^1H (C_6D_6 , 298 K) δ 8.17 [d, 4H, Ph], 7.27–7.11 [12H, m, Ph and Ar*], 6.50 [s, α -CH, MgNC₄H₄], 6.13 [s, 4H, β -CH, MgNC₄H₄], 4.48 [m, 2H, CH, ⁱPr, NAr*], 4.10 [s, 1H, NH], 3.35 [m, 24H, OCH₂, THF], 2.79 [m, 2H, CH, ⁱPr, NHAr*], 1.34 [d, 6H, CH₃, ⁱPr, NAr*], 1.27 [m, 24H, CH₂, THF], 1.06 [d, 6H, CH₃, ⁱPr, NAr*], 0.92 [d, 12H, CH₃, ⁱPr, NHAr*]. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (C_6D_6 , 298 K) δ 149.9, 146.5, 142.9, 142.5, 139.0 [C_{quaternary}, Ph and Ar*], 136.6 [CH, Ph], 128.5 [α -CH, MgNC₄H₄], 127.3 [CH, Ph], 127.1 [CH, Ph], 124.5, 123.6, 121.3, 120.5 [CH, Ar*], 107.0 [β -CH, MgNC₄H₄], 68.2 [O–CH₂, THF], 28.2 [CH, ⁱPr, NAr*], 27.7 [CH, ⁱPr, NHAr*] 25.8 [CH, ⁱPr, NAr*], 25.3 [CH₂, THF], 24.23 [CH₃, ⁱPr, NHAr*], 23.6 [CH₃, ⁱPr, NAr*].

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